

Building the Legal Knowledge Graph for Smart Compliance Services in Multilingual Europe

Welcome to Issue #2 of the **Lynx Newsletter**! During the past months, the Consortium has been putting a lot of effort into reach the main objectives of the project, and, as a consequence, the pilots are almost finished. Now, the Lynx consortium has set up a **Lynx Webinar Series for 2020/2021** to bring the project itself as well as the most outstanding achievements to SMEs, LegalTech companies and the public. **The first webinar is scheduled for the 10/12/2020, 10.30am CET.**

The **Lynx YouTube channel** has been also released and, to inaugurate the channel, a **Lynx Overview** video has been shot and edited. In this video, Elena Montiel-Ponsoda, as project coordinator, explains the challenges that the consortium faced and the features that will bring the Lynx Services beyond the state-of-the-art.

Lynx will also be present at one of the most relevant international conferences on innovative Language Technologies, META-FORUM. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this year **META-FORUM 2020** goes virtual. But that does not mean you have to miss anything. Follow the links in this newsletter to check the programme and to register to this conference.

Lynx's general usage scenarios and how we enable them from an architectural viewpoint is the main topic of Artem Revenko's (Semantic Web Company) post. This post addresses the **requirements posed by legal consultancy experts** and **how the consortium has designed and implemented the Lynx Services Platform (LySP).**

Take a look to the newsletter body for further information on the webinars and more, and remember to follow us on our social media channels to keep you posted on the pilots release.

Thank you for your attention.

The Lynx consortium.

Lynx Webinar Series

To bring the project itself as well as the results to our specified target audiences, the Lynx consortium has set-up a Lynx Webinar Series for 2020 / 2021.

The following webinars are scheduled:

1. Webinar 1: Lynx overall introduction

When: 10.12.2020, 10.30am CET (1 hour)

Registration:

<https://register.gotowebinar.com/register/6724354041352177932>

2. Webinar 2: 3 Business Cases on top of the Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph

When: 14.1.2021, 10.30am CET

Registration:

<https://attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/3694859758021614093>

3. Webinar 3: The Lynx Services Platform (LySP) - Part 1: Overview

When: 11/02/2021, 11.30am CET

Registration:

<https://attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/5556043772288317453>

4. Webinar 4: The Lynx Services Platform (LySP) - Part 2: The Services

When: 18/02/2021, 10.30am CET

Registration:

<https://attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/6255506890391068941>

5. Final Event: Lynx - Compliance made easy

When: 17/03/2020; 09.30 - 12.00pm CET

Registration:

<https://attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/1747701631044349709>

Webinar 1: Lynx - Compliance made easy. Free Webinar on LegalTech & Compliance Services

The main objective of the Lynx research and innovation project is to create an ecosystem of smart cloud services to better manage compliance, based on a Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG) that integrates and links multilingual and heterogeneous compliance data sources including legislation, case law, standards, regulations and other private contracts, besides others.

Lynx webinar, 10/12/2020, 10.30am CET

Register here: <https://register.gotowebinar.com/register/6724354041352177932>

This webinar is the kick off of a webinar series of in total 4 webinars taking place between December 2020 and March 2021 (Webinar 1: Lynx overview, Webinar 2: Business Cases, Webinar 3: Technology of Lynx, Webinar 4: The Lynx Services) as well as a virtual event taking place on 17th of March 2021, 09.30 - 12.00pm CET

including panel discussions and expert sessions on Lynx related topics (knowledge graphs, legaltech, compliance solutions, etc).

This webinar provides an overview of and insights in:

- **The Lynx project.** Elena Montiel Ponsoda, Lynx project lead, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
- **Legal Knowledge Graph: What is this & what is it good for.** Martin Kaltenböck, Lynx Innovation Manager, Co-Founder and CFO of Semantic Web Company, SWC
- **The Lynx Legal Knowledge Graph Model.** Victor Rodriguez Doncel, Lynx Scientific Manager, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
- **Lynx Services Platform (LySP): Architecture & Services.** Artem Revenko, Director of Research & Innovation, SWC
- **The 3 Pilots of Lynx: labor law, contract management, geothermal energy compliance.** Christian Sageder, Managing Director, Cybly GmbH

Lynx Project Overview

Lynx YouTube channel

The Lynx YouTube channel contains all the videos related to the Lynx project. For an overview of the project with challenges and main features, visit our YouTube channel. Soon we will publish a set of videos with demos of the pilot. Stay tuned!

Piloting the European Language Grid

META-FORUM 2020

[META-FORUM](#) is the international conference on innovative Language Technologies for a multilingual information society. The event brings together a diverse audience: Experts from research and industry will meet to discuss the latest news and to learn more about new developments, projects and initiatives from the European Language Grid and Language Technology community.

Selected Highlights:

- European Language Grid Release 2: Public demonstration
- Presentation of the ten ELG Pilot Projects from Open Call #1
- Feature your company or research group in the ELG
- Language Technology and AI: Building Bridges in the EU
- News from the language communities and from industry
- Virtual project expo featuring 30+ projects

Programme: <https://www.european-language-...>

Register free of charge: <https://www.european-language-...>

Lynx poster for the META-FORUM 2020

Lynx project: Compliance Services for Multilingual Europe

Lynx Service Platform architecture

Orchestrating legal NLP services for a portfolio of use cases

"In this post, I focus on general usage scenarios and how we enable them from an architectural point of view. But the [Lynx project](#) is much more than that! The individual services are state-of-the-art models customized to the legal domain. Every use case implements a unique solution to the below-mentioned challenges as a web application. We are glad to tell you more!..."

[Go to the post](#)

Use Case #3: Geothermal Energy

Geothermal Energy is an emerging source of

sustainable energy. Its application is expected to show accelerating growth driven by the need for the global energy transition. To achieve sustainable and controlled growth, modernisation of legislation and regulations, as well as industry standards and best practices, are required. Stakeholders – such as project developers, regulators and engineers – typically struggle to find this information, resulting in delayed application and imposing additional risks. The Lynx project aims to demonstrate how comprehensive legal taxonomies (as part of Legal Knowledge Graphs) help the user to find and select relevant regulatory documents (e.g. permits) and recommended reading on safety and environmental risks. For this pilot, it is essential to find and correctly link entities from the regulations to taxonomies (in the enrichment phase) and to quickly and reliably estimate the semantic similarity between the user's document and the collected documents. Moreover, to improve the accessibility and discoverability of data it is essential to translate the documents automatically.

Consortium

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